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Christian Couple and Divorce in Nigeria: A Biblical Perspective

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Abstract

Divorce is the process of terminating a marriage or marital union. It usually entails cancelling or reorganizing of legal duties and responsibilities of marriage, thus dissolving the matrimonial bonds between a married couple under the rule of law of the particular country or state. This paper examines some factors that lead to divorce in Nigeria and possibly Africa as a whole. While it is abundantly clear that God intended marriage to be a permanent union, there are also two grounds, controversial though they be, where the Bible appears to concede divorce and remarriage. It concludes that, the word “cleave” could be translated literally by the word “glued.” Marriage in the eyes of God is a relationship in which a man and a woman are “glued” together and the only thing that can separate them is death, and thereby recommend that, God’s position pertaining sexual union has not changed: no sex before marriage; no sex outside marriage. Christian homes should be citadels of peace and joy where water of sexuality is freely and joyfully shared between husbands and wives. This ‘sexual ethical teaching’ is an urgent need in the society today.

Keywords: Divorce, Marriage, Union, Christian Home, Sexuality

Introduction

There are numerous Bible passages on divorce, separation, and remarriage, such as Deut. 24: 1-4, Mal. 2:16, Matt. 5:31-32, Matt. 19:3-9, Mark 10: 2-12, Luke 16:18, Rom.7 :1-3 and I Cor. 7:10-11, 12-16. The basic passage in the Bible regarding divorce is Matt. 19:3-9. This is the only place where there is concerned and if we are clear on this passage; we have the teaching of Christ on the subject of divorce and remarriage in full.

Divorce is the opposite of all that marriage entails. The Greek word for divorce is *αποστασιον* (*apostasion*). It means a defection, to cause to withdraw. Its verb form is *απολθο* (*apothuo*), meaning to let loose from, let go free as a husband putting away his wife or a wife putting away her husband. However, Divorce in Biblical terminology is synonymous with driving out. When one partner in the marriage maltreats the other partner to the extent that he or she would abandon the matrimonial home, divorce has begun.

Some Contributory Factors to Divorce in Nigeria

This section gives some factors that lead to divorce in Nigeria and possibly Africa as a whole;

- *Barrenness*: One of the main causes of divorce in Nigeria is barrenness, especially in a cultural setting where too much emphasis is laid on child bearing as the purpose of marriage.
- *Leadership Struggle*: Some divorces are caused by the unwillingness of the wife to submit to her husband. The Bible teaches on leadership in the home. The Bible admonishes wives to recognize and subject themselves to the leadership or hardship of the husband (Eph. 5:22-24). Man must lead in love, women must submit in love; both must work as a team to preserve their marriage. Failure to do this causes divorce.
- *Economic Control*: Many Christian homes have been ruined because of the struggle for economic control in the family. Unhealthy rivalry in the economic pursuits may cause divorce. When spouses try to do outdo each other in a career, or in some endeavour, the marriage may be in trouble.
- *Lack of Sexual Fulfillment*: This is a serious problem. Importance on the part of the husband results in lack of sexual fulfillment on the part of the wife. Lack of sexual fulfillment in marriage may lead to adultery on the part of the wife, hence divorce.
- *Marriage of Convenience*: This is very often results from pregnancy outside of wedlock. As a common practice in Nigeria, such persons are forced to marry, and thus it is called a marriage of convenience. The basis of such marriage is sex love, and because

there is no agape love in the marriage, it can easily give way to divorce at a little provocation.

- *Home Management:* In most of the Nigerian ethnic group it is held that a man has no home until he is married. The wife therefore is traditionally looked unto as the manager of the home in many respects. Where the wife does not fulfill these expirations of home management the husband would either consider a divorce or taking a second wife.
- *Influence of Parents in Choosing a Wife:* Very often parents have imposed a wife or husband on their son or daughter respectively for some reasons best known to them. Parents would insist that their son or daughter marry a particular person even if that is not the choice of the son or daughter. In many cases, marriages contracted by parents on behalf of their children end up in divorce.
- *In-law's Interference After Marriage:* sometimes interference from the families of spouses may lead to divorce.
- *Influence of Non-Christian Cultures:* The Bible says "Bad company corrupts good manner. It appears that of all known religions in the world only Christianity strictly forbids divorce. Judaism which has some affinity to Christianity does not frown much at divorce. Divorce is commonly practice among Muslims, traditional worshipers and others. Such divorce practices among non-Christians badly influence some Christians.

Biblical Exceptions

While it is abundantly clear that God intended marriage to be permanent union, there are also two grounds, controversial though they be, where the Bible appears to concede divorce and remarriage. The two Biblical exceptions are divorce on the ground of Sexual Immorality and divorce on the ground of religious conversion.

A. Divorce on the ground of Sexual Immorality

Some Christians have taken the statement of Jesus in Matt. 19:9 as a ground for divorce, where Jesus clearly states that if there must be a separation, fornication is the only admissible.

B. Divorce on the ground of Religious Conversion

Another passage in the Bible where some Christians point to as exception clause for divorce is 1 Cor.7:13, 15, where it is seen that the

unbeliever who deserts his wife should be divorce and that in such a situation the believer is free to marry. Also, if due to the conversion of one of the spouses to Christianity, peace has disappeared in a certain marriage, divorce is permissible.

Spiritual Application

It should be noted first of all categorical statement God had made on divorce “I hate divorce”, says the Lord God of Israel (Mal. 2:16). This is God’s view on divorce. God is unalterably opposed to divorce. It was never included in His plan for man. No divorce has ever had His approval. Though God seems to have conceded divorce in some special instances, it does not correspond with the will of God as does marriage itself. Christian must do everything possible to prevent divorce in his or her marriage. Divorce is not only a disobedience to God, it also disrupts the society. God instituted marriage in order to avoid dissolution of society.

On Barrenness, Barrenness should not be and is not a ground for divorce. Rather the Christian should be able to accept the situation of barrenness, trusting in the sovereign will of God. Procreation should be seen as secondary purpose of marriage rather than its primary purpose. On Moses, the Pharisees did not actually quote Moses correctly. Moses never propounded any theory of Divorce, but he recognized the fact that divorce was a common practice in Israel. Therefore the purpose of Moses’ command to Israel was to regulate the practice of divorce among the Israelites, to raise the standards of marital and sexual behaviour among the people.

Sexual immorality as a ground for divorce is very logical. In Exodus 20:14. God specifically commands “you shall not commit adultery.” When God instituted marriage, He said man and woman becomes one flesh in marriage. Adultery or fornication is a violation of God’s law in the first place and violation of marriage vow in the second place and consequently, by its nature is essentially act of divorcement. The Adulterous or the fornicator is already a divorced person. Physical separation is only recognition of the fact that divorce had taken place already through the act of adultery. In short what Christ is saying here is that a marriage which has been spiritually separated by means of adultery could be physically separated too. Nevertheless, even when the case of adultery or fornication is established, the principle of agape love

can be applied thus paving way for forgiveness, reconciliation and restoration. Concerning religious conversion, divorce is wrong but in a situation where the partner who is not a Christian initiates divorce, the Christian should concede to divorce only after every attempt at reconciliation has failed.

Another issue is that, should converted polygamist drive away all his wives except the first one to remain monogamy? It is not the Christian solution for a converted polygamist to drive away all but his first wife. That would be unjust and irresponsible behaviour from a husband who has made a commitment to care for his wives (Num.30: 1-2, 16). However, only God can work out a solution which will not hurt people unnecessarily, Prayer and patience are the ways for the polygamist to find God's answer to his situation.

Divorce and Children

This subject would not be exhausted unless we said a word about the only really innocent parties in any case of separation, the child or children. No matter what the basis of divorce or separation may be, the child that lives in a divided home, without one of his parents, always lives under an emotional strain that ordinary children do not have to bear and it will leave its mark upon his life. It destroys the bright and eager faith of the child, makes him feel as though he has been rejected, and torments him for years.

Conclusion

Jesus in quoting Matthew 19:4-6 is indicating God's original intention in the marriage tie. When the animals were created God made a male animal, and then, by a separate creation, he made a female animal. This is true of dogs, horses, cattle, and all other animals. But when God created man, woman was not a separate creation; she was a part of the original. God formed woman from a part of the man which He had already created so that in a very literal sense she was one flesh with the man. In the marriage union a man and a woman revert to the original. In the eyes of the Creator they are no longer two persons, but one. That is why God says through Adam, for this cause shall a man leave father and mother, and shall cleave to his wife." (Gen.2:24) The word "Cleave" could be translated literally by the word "glued." Marriage in the eyes of

God is a relationship in which a man and a woman are “glued” together and the only thing that can separate them is death.

Recommendations

1. To prevent divorce, husband and the wife should individually and corporately be properly related to God.
2. Christians should possess Self-discipline, prudence and moderation as God’s requirements to enjoy their sexual lives.
3. Consequently, Christian couples must be available for one another. They should not expose their partners to sexual temptations. God’s position pertaining sexual union has not changed: no sex before marriage; no sex outside marriage (Heb. 13: 4).
4. Christian homes should be citadels of peace and joy where water of sexuality is freely and joyfully shared between husbands and wives. This ‘sexual ethical teaching’ is an urgent need in the society today.
5. African elders and the church of God should set the pace for young ones and adults to follow.

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